

Editorial

From its start, the *SKASE Journal of Translation and Interpretation* has been a Diamond Open Access journal. This means that neither the readers nor the authors pay for its services. As a consequence, we cannot afford fees for reviewers or payments to the editors for the services to the journal. We are grateful to our universities for their support. The Pavol Jozef Šafárik University in Košice hosts the journal website as well as the email address and offers technical support. The University of Innsbruck pays for a student assistant giving editorial support. In addition, the Slovak Association for the Study of English provides the funding for assigning a doi to each article published in our journal.

In order to maintain a high standard of quality for the articles we publish, we have to appeal to reviewers. Like many other journals, also many that charge for subscriptions, we do not pay for reviews. We hope that they find the opportunity to read about potentially interesting ideas at an early stage and the feeling to make an essential contribution to the development of the field a sufficient reward for the efforts. Once a year, in the July issue, we publish a list of names with the colleagues who helped us by reviewing a paper we received. On request the journal can also issue a certificate.

We are grateful to the reviewers who support our journal and we are continuously looking for ways to make their efforts more meaningful and less burdensome. Last year we introduced a review form. This year, we piloted a preliminary evaluation step. All submissions are first evaluated by one of the editors. The results are discussed in an editorial meeting. Papers for which we judge that they would be unlikely to be accepted are rejected at this stage. Other papers go through our usual peer review process. In this way, the quality of the papers received by reviewers should be better. For authors, the additional step should not lead to a longer processing period. For papers rejected at this stage, the advantage is that they get an earlier decision.

In the twelve months ending 30 November, we received 87 manuscripts for our regular issues. Of these, 40 were not sent out for review and two were withdrawn. The others are in different stages of the reviewing process. In addition, we published a special issue on empirical translation and interpreting studies in September. It was guest-edited by Silvana Deilen and Ekatarina Lapshinova-Koltunski. For special issues, our policy is that they appear in addition to the two regular issues we produce in June and in December.

In this issue, you will find six articles. We hope you will enjoy reading them. We invite authors to submit their manuscripts through the journal's email address and we invite scholars willing to review manuscripts to contact us.

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